
A Study on Employability Skills among Arts College Students

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ABSTRACT

Rising graduate unemployment is largely attributed to inadequate employability skills despite academic qualifications. This study assesses the employability skills of three hundred final year Arts college students in Chengalpattu district, it does so against the background of a national problem where only 8.25% of graduates get jobs that match their degrees, as mentioned in the Economic Survey 2024–25. Survey method was adopted by using simple random sampling technique, data were collected through a researcher-developed Employability Skills Scale measuring communication, teamwork, problem-solving, time management, adaptability, digital skills, and self-motivation. Results indicate moderate skill levels and significant gender differences. This study emphasizes targeted training, skill-development programs, and technology integration to improve graduates' employability.

Introduction:

This study focuses on third-year Arts College students who are nearing graduation and examines whether they possess the employability skills required for a successful transition into the workforce. It explores students' readiness to face real-world professional demands, such as job interviews and entry into organizational roles, and assesses their confidence and preparedness. This study highlights the

importance of employability skills in reducing graduate unemployment, as skill deficiencies often limit access to suitable job opportunities. It further investigates potential interventions, including AI-focused workshops, mock interviews, digital skill training through online courses, and industry-linked experiential projects. The research aims to identify existing skill gaps and propose practical strategies to strengthen students' employability, thereby preparing students to meet the expectations of today's competitive job market.

Definition of Employability Skills:

In today's dynamic business era, improving employability in management education is considered a major challenge by all educational institutions. Management training focuses on developing a wide range of management knowledge and skills. There is a high emphasis on the performance of job applicants, which requires job-matching skills. Students are expected to improve their communication and teamwork abilities in addition to subject-based assignments. By integrating employers with expectations and the nature of work, this article emphasizes recent research findings, employment skills practices, and reviews such as job definition, employment potential, and employer needs and requirements. In the twenty-first century, India's educational system has changed significantly. Many management companies still follow the traditional teaching method. The need of this training is to bridge the gap between academics and career.

Review of Related Literature:

Gowsalya and Kumar., (2016). examined the level of employability skills among Arts and Science college students in the Namakkal district of Tamil Nadu. The study adopted a quantitative survey design and employed stratified and probability sampling techniques during the initial stage of questionnaire administration. Postgraduate students from the top five selected Arts and Science colleges in the district constituted the study population, totalling 1,775 students. From this population, 20% (155 students) were approached for data collection. Of these, 140 valid responses were obtained through proportional representation from each selected college and were included in the final analysis. Structural Equation Modelling (SEM) was used as the statistical tool for data analysis. The findings revealed that there was no significant relationship between employability skills and parents' educational background.

Idaka and Uzoechi., (2016). investigated the influence of gender and age on the acquisition of employability skills among University students in Imo State. The study sample consisted of 618 final-year students from the 2013/2014 academic session. Data were collected using the Employability Skills

Acquisition Questionnaire (ESAQ). The data were analysed using population *t*-tests, independent *t*-tests, and Analysis of Variance (ANOVA). The findings indicated that the level of employability skills acquisition among university students was significantly high, and that both gender and age had a significant influence on employability skills acquisition.

Need of the study:

The Economic Survey 2024–25 reveals that only 8.25% of graduates in India secure employment that aligns with their field of study, highlighting a significant skills gap in the workforce. More than 50% of graduates and 44% of postgraduates are employed in low-skill jobs, largely due to inadequate vocational training and outdated educational practices. The survey emphasizes the urgent need for educational reforms that better align academic curricula with labour market requirements and enhance employment opportunities for educated youth..

A deeper look at employment trends

The data further reveals the distribution of jobs according to skill levels and educational attainment:

Education Level	Elementary	Semi-skilled	High Competency Skilled	Specialised
10 Years/Informal Education	32.13%	66.30%	0.29%	1.28%
12 Years of Education	19.25%	72.18%	2.79%	5.77%
Graduate	3.22%	50.30%	8.25%	38.23%
Postgraduate	0.96%	28.12%	7.67%	63.26%

The data illustrates how workers with higher educational qualifications, such as graduates and postgraduates, are still largely employed in non-specialised roles.

This data was taken from Times of India

source:

http://m.timesofindia.com/article/show/117818374.cms?utm_source=perplexity&utm_source=contentofinterest&utm_medium=text&utm_campaign=cppst

Objectives:

- 1.To compare the Employability Skills of Arts students studying under different management.
- 2.To examine the difference in the Employability Skills of Arts College Students with respect to gender.

Hypotheses :

1. There is no significant difference between type of management of Arts College Students in the Employability Skills.
2. There is no significant difference between male and female of Arts college students in the Employability Skills.

Methodology:

The method adopted for this study is survey. A total of 300 Arts college students from Chengalpattu District was selected using a simple random sampling technique. Data was collected using the Employability Skills Scale developed by the researcher with the guidance of the research supervisor.

Hypothesis: 1

There is no significant difference in the Employability Skills of Arts College students with respect to type of management.

Type of management	N	Mean	SD	't'-value	LS
Government	160	150.41	17.66	1.41	P <0.05
Private	140	153.3	17.75		

From the above table, it shows that the calculated 't'- value is lesser than table value at 0.05 level, which indicating no significant difference between Government and Private arts college students in their Employability Skills. Hence, the null hypothesis is accepted. Since Naan Mudhalvan Scheme is giving many training programmes equally to the Private and Government Arts college students for developing their Employability Skills.

Hypothesis: 2

There is no significant difference in the Employability Skills of Arts College students with respect to gender.

Gender	N	Mean	SD	't' value	LS
Male	200	150.41	17.66	2.97	P >0.05
Female	100	144.44	15.88		

From the table, it is evident that the calculated t -value is greater than the table value at the 0.05 level of significance. This indicates a statistically significant difference between male and female Arts college students in their employability skills. The Employability skills observed among male students are greater than the female students; therefore, the null hypothesis is rejected. Since the exposure to extracurricular activities, internships, part-time work, and skill-oriented training programmes attended by the male students show high ratio of participation.

Findings:

1. There is a significant difference in employability skills of arts college students with respect to gender. The Employability Skills observed among male students are greater than the female students, exposure to extracurricular activities, internships, part-time work, and skill-oriented training programmes.
2. There is no significant difference in Employability Skills of arts college students with respect to type of management.

Educational Implications:

Colleges should provide more activities such as workshops, placement training, communication practice sessions, career guidance programs, and problem-solving tasks. Offering real-life learning experiences can help students better understand workplace needs and enhance their skills. Additionally, teachers should adopt effective instructional methods and relevant technologies to strengthen students' learning. Particularly English faculties can organize refresher courses focusing on communication skills for further enhance in Employability Skill.

Conclusion:

The present study examined the Employability skills of Arts college students with specific reference to gender and type of management. The findings revealed that male students possessed a significantly higher level of employability skills compared to female students, highlighting the need for strengthened skill-development initiatives in higher education. However, no significant difference was found among Arts college students with respect to the type of management. Enhancing Employability Skills will help students become more competitive and better prepared for future careers.

Reference:

- Gowsalya, G., & Kumar, A. (2016). A study on the factors affecting employability skills among college students in Namakkal District of Tamil Nadu. *International Journal of Commerce and Management Research*, 2(11), 9-14.
- Idaka, I. E., & Uzoечи, L. I. (2016). Gender, age and employability skills acquisition among university students in Imo state, Nigeria. *International Journal of Innovative Education Research*, 4(4), 6-15.
- Education, T. (2025, February 1). Economic Survey reveals only 8.25% of graduates have jobs matching their qualifications. *The Times of India*.
http://m.timesofindia.com/articleshow/117818374.cms?utm_source=perplexity&utm_source=contentofinterest&utm_medium=text&utm_campaign=cppst